

Translation Techniques of Representative Speech Act Uttered by the Main Character in the “*Wonka*” Movie

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Abstract. Translation techniques serve as a method to analyze and classify how translation equivalence works. There are 18 translation techniques according to (Molina and Albir, 2002). This research focuses on translation techniques and pragmatic speech act theory in the dialogue of the main character in the film subtitle “*Wonka*” which released in 2023. Data collection is carried out by observing the film being analyzed, collecting data obtained in the film, and analyzing the translation techniques. The method used in this research was descriptive qualitative method. The researcher found 32 data in the film. The most found translation techniques is established equivalent (31,2%). The least translation techniques found are modulation (3,1%) and literal translation (3,1%). The other are borrowing (18,7%), discursive creation (18,7%), reduction (12,5%), linguistic compression (6,2%), and compensation (6,2%). The researcher also found 15 data of speech act representative in the film.

Keywords: Film, Translation Techniques, Speech Act, Subtitle, Linguistic

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

According to Astiningsih & Nugroho (2024) translation has a meaning to transfer a messages and information from one language to another language. In translation there are two languages involved, namely the source language and the target language (Isnaini & Nugroho, 2022). The source language itself is the language that is translated into another language. Also called the language used as an introduction in foreign language teaching. To learn a foreign language, we need a source language first. without a source language we will not be able to translate a foreign language into Indonesian. It is like the source language from which the loan words originate (Iriawan & Nugroho, 2023). While the target language is the language used to translate written text into the final language. This target language is the language into which the source text is translated. If you are discussing a source language, you have the source, but if you are discussing the target language, the source is from the source language to translate it (Meilany & Nugroho, 2023). In translating a language, a theory is needed. In the field of translation there are several theories or ways to translate language such as translation techniques, translation methods, translation strategies, translation procedures, and etc. In the translation method there are 8 methods for translating. In the translation procedure there are 24 procedures for translating. While in translation techniques there are 18 techniques for translating. And to analyze the data the researchers want to use the translation theory, namely translation techniques by Molina and Albir (2002). In translating, there must be quality translation (Nababan et al, 2012).

Apart from that, to translate a language correctly, linguistic theory is also needed. According to the KBBI (Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa, 2016), linguistics is the science of language or the scientific study of language. Linguistics contributes to studying, providing and even researching the area of translation, while translation itself is directly related to linguistics, both at the theoretical and practical levels. In translating language, linguistic theory is needed, one of which is pragmatics. theories in pragmatics itself such as deixis, speech act, implicature, hedges, and etc. In this research,

to analyze the data the researchers want to use linguistic theory, namely pragmatics. The theory in pragmatics that the researchers want to use is speech act. Speech act theory was put forward by John Searle who classified speech acts into 5 types, namely declarations, representatives, expressive, directives, and commissive. Speech act itself is an action expressed through speech. With speech acts, speakers can carry out several actions such as asking, requesting, ordering, or refusing in the sentences spoken. The type of speech act that will be used to analyze the data is representative. Representatives are kinds of speech acts that states what the speakers believe to be the case or not. Such as statement, fact, and descriptions.

In this research the researcher used a musical drama entitled “Wonka” which was released in 2023 in cinemas. This film has a musical and humorous nuance. Played by the main character named Timothee Chalamet who becomes the character Wonka. This film was directed by Paul King. In this research the researcher only focus on the main character in this film namely Wonka. The researcher will analyze 18 translation techniques (Molina and Albir 2002) as well as speech act representative in dialogue in the film Wonka. The aim of this research is to find out what techniques translations are in the Wonka film and the speech act representatives in the film.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This research used linguistic data, namely pragmatic. Pragmatics is a science that studies the conditions of language use in human communication which are determined by the context of its use. There is a social context and a social context. Social context is the context that arises as a result of interactions between members of society in a particular social and cultural group. Meanwhile, the social context is a context that is determined by the position of community members in the social institutions found in certain social and cultural groups. In many ways, pragmatics is similar to semantics because both study meaning. The difference is that pragmatics is closely tied to context, while semantics is free from context. So, in pragmatics, there must be a context for what is being discussed and who is being discussed. If there is no context then it is called semantic. For example, "Padang Restaurant", semantically refers to a restaurant located in Padang City. However, pragmatically, this phrase describes a restaurant that serves typical Padang cuisine, West Sumatra.

The theory used in pragmatics is speech act by John Searle. Speech act is a theory which assumes that the meaning of linguistic expressions can be explained by following the rules that apply when carrying out speech acts, such as reprimanding, affirming, ordering, calling, promising, questioning and requesting. In general, Searle identifies three basic dimensions that differ from one type to another, namely locutionary acts, illocutionary acts, and perlocutionary acts. Locutionary acts are speech acts to express something with words, phrases and sentences according to the meaning contained. Illocutionary acts are speech acts to do something with a specific purpose. Perlocutionary acts are speech acts intended to influence the addressee. From these three dimensions, Searle developed a taxonomy of speech acts consisting of five categories, namely declarations, representatives, expressive, commissive, and directives.

Table 1. Classification of Speech Act

Classification of Speech Act	Definition	Example
Representative	Representative are kinds of speech act that states what the speakers believe to be the case or not. The type of this speech act such as fact, statement, and descriptions.	The earth is flat
Declarations	A type of speech act that can change a person's status through his or her utterance.	I sentenced you 8 years in jail
Expressive	A type of speech act where someone expresses what they feel.	I'm really sorry
Directives	A type of speech act where someone ask another person to obey what they ask or orders.	Could you lend me a pen, please?
Commissive	A type of speech act where someone commit themselves to some future action.	I'll be back

Based on the table 1 above are the classification of speech act according to John Searle. But for this research, the researchers use the representative speech act. Representative is a type of speech act that is analyzed based on facts, descriptions and statements. The researchers also analyze the type of speech act in the film is direct speech act or indirect speech act in the film "Wonka".

Apart from that, this research used translation techniques to analyze the data. Translation is interpreting the source language text into the target language with the aim of ensuring that the external meaning of both languages is the same and ensuring that the composition of the source language is maintained as closely as possible, but not so close that the composition of the target language becomes very unclear (Normalita & Nugroho, 2023; Muhaya & Nugroho, 2024). In translating, a theory is needed and can make the reader understand what is being translated. A correct translation can only be called correct if the reader understands what we are translating. If the reader still cannot understand, it means that the translation made is still not correct. Therefore, theory is very important in translating. In this research, the researcher used 18 translation techniques by Molina and Albir (2002).

Table 2. Translation Techniques by Molina and Albir

No.	Translation Techniques	Definition	Example
1.	Adaptation	Adaptation techniques are techniques used to adapt terms to suit elements of TL culture.	ST : As white as snow TT : <i>Seputih kapas</i>
2.	Amplification	This technique is applied to several SL sentences that require additional words when translated into TL.	ST : Ramadhan TT : <i>Bulan puasa kaum muslim</i>
3.	Borrowing	Borrowing techniques can be done by borrowing or introducing terms from SL sentences as a whole.	ST : Mixer TT : Mixer
4.	Calque	The calque technique is a translation technique that translates words or phrases lexically and structurally.	ST : Directorate General TT : <i>Direktorat Jendral</i>
5.	Compensation	Compensation techniques are used to introduce new stylistic elements when the terms used in the language cannot be placed in the same position in the language.	ST : A pair of scissors TT : <i>Sebuah gunting</i>
6.	Description	The description translation technique functions to provide an overview of the terms contained in SL sentences.	ST : Arem-arem TT : <i>Indonesian tradisional food</i>
7.	Discursive Creation	A technique in translation where the translator translates language out of the context.	ST : Impetigore TT : <i>Perempuan tanah jahannam</i>

8.	Established Equivalent	Established equivalence techniques can be used to translate SL sentences into terms that are commonly or familiarly used among the SL community.	ST : Good man TT : <i>Laki-laki baik</i>
9.	Generalization	Generalization techniques are used to translate specific terms in SL sentences into more commonly known terms in SL sentences.	ST : Penthouse TT : <i>Tempat tinggal</i>
10.	Linguistic Amplification	Techniques that include the addition of linguistic elements.	ST : It was a good performance TT : <i>Itu adalah penampilan yang bagus</i>
11.	Linguistic Compression	Techniques that involve reducing linguistic elements.	ST : Don't eat it TT : <i>Jangan dimakan</i>
12.	Literal Translation	Literal translation technique is a technique that translates elements of words, phrases and sentences contained in SL directly (word for word).	ST : Killing two birds with one stone TT : <i>Membunuh dua burung dengan satu batu</i>
13.	Modulation	There are times when translators are asked to translate SL sentences while maintaining the meaning of the SL sentence by changing the point of view or the core focus in the SL sentence itself.	ST : Nobody doesn't like it TT : <i>Semua orang menyukainya</i>
14.	Particularization	Particularization translation techniques can be used to translate a term used in SL into a more specific or specific term.	ST : Air transportation TT : <i>Pesawat</i>

15.	Reduction	Reduction techniques are used to condense the message content in SL sentences.	ST : Prabowo the president of republic Indonesia TT : <i>Prabowo Subianto</i>
16.	Substitution	Substitution techniques can be used to translate language elements produced by gestures, intonation and so on.	ST : Put your hand on your heart TT : Thank you
17.	Transposition	The transposition translation technique is carried out by adjusting the word order in the SL accordingly with a TL structure.	ST : Adept TT : <i>Sangat terampil</i>
18.	Variation	The variation technique functions to translate SL sentences by considering several elements contained in the language as in dialect.	ST : I want to go to London TT : <i>Aku mau pergi ke London</i>

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a descriptive qualitative method. Descriptive qualitative research is a method of research that is focused on understanding a phenomenon by examining its characteristics and qualities (Nugroho et al., 2020; . We use this type of research when we want to explore a topic that has not been studied in depth before, or when we want to gain a better understanding of a previously studied topic but using a different perspective and gain valuable insights in the process. The data from this research was taken from the film *Wonka*. The researcher took this data by looking at the subtitles in the *Wonka* film on a site called *Drakor Kita* (<https://drakorkita.in/detail/wonka-2023-8buu/>). The first thing to do to find the data is to watch the *Wonka* film, then collect the data that has been obtained in the film, identify the data into 18 translation techniques and the type of speech act representative in the film.

This research uses descriptive qualitative method to analyse the data. The researchers use this method because this analysis is based on quality. The quality of the translation in *Wonka* films. The unit of analysis is based on conversational dialogue in the *Wonka* film. Here the researcher only focus on the dialogue of the main character, namely *Wonka*. The data from this analysis was taken from the subtitles in the *Wonka* film. And watched on a site called *Drakor Kita*. In this research, steps are needed for the research to be correct. The steps to carry out this research are:

- 1) Selecting Data: The researcher took analysis data from subtitles in the *Wonka* film.
- 2) Extract Data: The researcher look for the Indonesian translation of *Wonka*'s dialogue.

- 3) Organizing Data: The researcher grouped all the data found from the subtitles in the Wonka film.

The following is the sequence of data analysis techniques used by researchers:

- 1) Identifying any data obtained into translation techniques and types of speech act representatives.
- 2) Making componential excerpt, this excerpt contains an explanation of each example of data analysis obtained.

Table 3. Componential Excerpt of The Data.

Source Language (English)	Target Language (Indonesian)	Type of Speech Act Representative	Translation Techniques
“Just for tonight.”	“Hanya untuk malam ini”	Statement	Established Equivalent

- 3) The final stage is the conclusion. In the conclusion we will know what translation techniques are more widely used and what types of representative speech are used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the analysis of the use of translation techniques and speech act representative from the movie Wonka which has been carried out by researcher can be seen in following table:

Table 4. Representative Speech Act Findings

Speech Act Representative	Type of Representative	Direct/Indirect Speech Act
“It must be his pants.”	Fact	Direct
“Unfortunately I’m not in a position to pay for a room sevice.”	Statement	Direct
“I’m something of magician inventorand chocolate maker.”	Fact	Direct
“Harvested from marsh in Peru.”	Description	Direct

“It will be completely no harm.”	Fact	Direct
“I got it from mail man in sinks”.	Fact	Direct
“Perhaps it’s a little cold for camping”.	Fact	Direct
“But all that’s about to change”.	Fact	Direct
“First thing tomorrow at galery gourmet, i plan to envail my most stunniest creation yet”.	Statement	Direct
“What a kind people”.	Fact	Direct
“The like which this world was never seen”.	Fact	Direct
“If you thought the chocolate was weird You’ll gonna hate what’s happen next”.	Fact	Direct
“Made of condensed tunder cloud and liquid sunny”.	Description	Direct
“We never had a lot of money but each week she brought home one cocoa bean”.	Fact	Direct
“we lived down in the river Just the two of us in perfect little world of us”.	Fact	Direct
TOTAL = 15		

From table 4, the researcher found 15 speech act representative and all of them are direct speech act. And there are the type of fact, statement, and description found in the data.

Table 5. Translation Techniques Findings

Translation Techniques	Quantity	Occurrence
Established Equivalent	10	31,2%
Borrowing	6	18,7%
Discursive Creation	6	18,7%
Reduction	4	12,5%
Compensation	2	6,2%
Linguistic Compression	2	6,2%
Modulation	1	3,1%
Literal Translation	1	3,1%
TOTAL	32	100%

From the tabel 5, the results shown there are 32 data of translation techniques. The techniques from the most to the less occurrence are established equivalent (31,2%), Borrowing (18,7%), Discursive creation (18,7%), Reduction (12,5%), linguistic compression (6,2%), Compensation (6,2%), Modulation (3,1%), and Literal translation (3,1%).

Discussion

Based on the data obtained, the translation techniques most widely used in Wonka film subtitles are established equivalent, borrowing, and discursive creation. From there it can be seen that the translator translates a text like a translation in general. And also found the type of speech act representative in the Wonka film. To show the researchers' point, the researchers present all of the translation techniques found in the film and 3 sample of speech act representative:

Excerpt 1

Wonka : "It must be his pants"

From the analysis, it is a representative speech act because that sentence is the type of sentence that is a fact not an order, promise or the other. And it is a direct speech act because the structure is declarative and the function is statement. The context is Wonka told Mr. Scrubitt that it must be from his pants.

Excerpt 2

Wonka : "Unfortunately I'm not in a position to pay for room service."

From the analysis, it is a representative speech act because that sentence is the type of sentence that is a statement not an order, promise or the other. And it is the same as the other sample, it is a direct speech act because the structure is declarative and the function is statement. The context is Wonka told Ms. Scrubitt that he could not pay for the room service.

Excerpt 3

Wonka : "Harvested from marsh in Peru."

From the analysis, it is a representative speech act because that sentence is the type of sentence that is a description not an order, promise or the other. It describes how is a hover chocolate made. And it is a direct speech act because the structure is declarative and the function is statement. The context is Wonka told Mr. Slugworth, Mr. Fickelgruber, and Mr. Prodnose that the hover chocolate was harvested from marsh in Peru.

Excerpt 4

ST : "Don't be ridiculous"

TT : "*Jangan konyol*"

From the analysis, it is called established equivalent because the translation above is a general translation. Everyone translates the words "dont be ridiculous" with "*jangan konyol*". The context is that Wonka talk to mr scrubitt about planning to sleep in the street.

Excerpt 5

ST : "Perhaps It's a little cold for camping."

TT : "*Mungkin agak dingin untuk bermalam.*"

From the analysis, it is called linguistic compression because the word "it is" is not translated while the word "it is" is a linguistic element. And the context is same with the data above that Wonka talk to mr scrubitt about planning to sleep in the street.

Excerpt 6

ST : "Thank you Ms. Scrubitt."

TT : "*Terimakasih Ms. Scrubitt.*"

From the analysis, it is called Borrowing because the word "Ms. Scrubitt" is not translated, it still the same. The context is that Wonka thanked Ms. Scrubitt for let him stay at her home.

Excerpt 7

ST : "I'm afraid that's true."

TT : "*Begitulah.*"

From the analysis, it is called discursive creation because the sentence that are translated is out of context or do not match the original meaning. The context is that Wonka talk to Ms. Scrubitt about he will work from tomorrow to pay the room rent.

Excerpt 8

ST : "It will be completely no harm."

TT : "*Ini tidak berbahaya.*"

From the analysis, it is called reduction because the word "completely" is not translated. It should be translated "*ini benar-benar tidak berbahaya*". The context is that Wonka told mr. Slugworth, mr. Fickelgruber, and mr. Prodnose that the hover chocolate is not dangerous.

Excerpt 9

ST : "That is a quiet handshake."

TT : "*Jabat tanganmu kuat.*"

From the analysis, it is called compensation because the word "handshake" is translated at the beginning of the sentence and not at the end according to the position of the word "handshake". The context is that Wonka shakes hands with Mr. Slugworth.

Excerpt 10

ST : "More than enough."

TT : "*Lebih dari cukup.*"

From the analysis, it is called literal translation because the sentence is translated word for word. More means "lebih", than means "dari", and enough means "cukup". The context is that Wonka told Ms. Scrubitt that all of the things she did to him was more than enough.

Excerpt 11

ST : "By this tomorrow I plan to make my fortune."

TT : "*Besok aku pasti punya banyak uang.*"

From the analysis, it is called modulation because in that sentence the translation has a change in Wonka's angle or it has a point of view of Wonka's utterances. The context is that Wonka told Mr. Scrubitt that he plans to make money tomorrow.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, there are 32 data of translation techniques found in the movie and 15 data of speech act representative. The most translation techniques found are Discursive creation (31,2%), Borrowing (18,7%), Discursive creation (18,7%). And the other are linguistic compression (6,2%), Reduction (12,5%), Compensation (6,2%). And the least translation techniques found are Modulation (3,1%) and Literal translation (3,1%). Also there are 15 speech act representative found in the movie and all of them are direct speech act. There are classified as a fact, there are also classified as statement, and description.

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